
Ethnomedicine Through a Multidisciplinary Lens: Bridging Tradition and Science

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores ethnomedicine through a multidisciplinary lens, bridging traditional cultural practices and modern biomedical science. Ethnomedicine, deeply rooted in indigenous knowledge systems, reflects the longstanding human relationship with nature, encompassing the use of plants, animals, and spiritual rituals for healing and maintaining health. Drawing from anthropology, sociology, botany, zoology, and history, this study highlights the cultural, ecological, and symbolic dimensions of traditional medical practices worldwide. Despite the dominance of modern medicine, ethnomedicine continues to serve as the primary health resource for a significant portion of the global population, emphasizing the importance of preserving biodiversity and cultural heritage. Integrating these ancient healing systems with contemporary medical approaches promises more holistic, sustainable, and personalized healthcare solutions. This paper emphasizes the value of respecting, studying, and integrating ethnomedicine to enrich global health systems while honoring the cultural identities and environmental wisdom embedded within these practices.

INTRODUCTION

The natural world is endowed with an abundance of resources sustaining life and offering remedies for ailments even before the advent of formal medical systems. From time immemorial, humans have turned to nature for survival, drawing nourishment, shelter, and healing from the forests they inhabited.¹ Early

hunter-gatherer communities relied on these ecosystems and played a crucial role in domesticating edible plants and discovering medicinal resources. Their deep connection to the land shaped their understanding of health, illness, and healing, forming the foundation of indigenous medical traditions that continue to persist today.ⁱⁱ

Forests have long served humans as the primary source for collecting raw materials for healing and treating injuries. The evidence of the use of plants for medicine is seen in the fossil record of the middle Palaeolithic period around 60,000 years ago.ⁱⁱⁱ As human societies transitioned from nomadic hunter-gatherers to more settled agricultural communities, their relationship with the natural world evolved, shaping their medical knowledge and healing traditions.

This development comes from the tangible reliance on forest ecosystems and the animistic belief systems that prevailed among forest-dwelling societies.^{iv} The profound human-forest relationship over the period began to be fostered by the combination of ritualist practice and animistic belief of the forest-dwelling traditional societies. They protected the area of the natural ecosystem in each region in which they existed by considering them sacred forests in many societies worldwide.^v This relationship between humans and forest ecosystems also began to serve them for medicinal purposes. The evidence comes from the preservation of knowledge within the various Indigenous communities across the globe. Building upon this intrinsic human-forest connection, ethnomedicine, the traditional medical knowledge and practices rooted in specific cultures, had emerged as a vital aspect to promote human health, longevity, and well-being.

Through generations of observation and practice, Indigenous peoples have identified and utilized numerous plants, minerals, and animal derivatives with medicinal properties to treat a wide range of illnesses. Often marginalized in modern medical discourse, these communities have maintained traditional ethnomedical practices, relying on their profound understanding of local species for healing and health maintenance. According to a report from the World Health Organisation, around 80 percent of people still rely on traditional medicines and herbs for their primary health care requirements.^{vi} Thus, over the ages, the use of forest produce for medicinal purposes by indigenous people has evolved significantly.

Ethnomedicine refers to traditional medical practices deeply embedded in various communities' culture and social structure. These practices involve using natural elements such as plants, minerals, and animals, combined with rituals and spiritual beliefs, to heal and maintain health. The World Health Organization (WHO) recognizes ethnomedicine under the broader umbrella of traditional medicine,

defining it as "the sum total of the knowledge, skills, and practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences indigenous to different cultures, used in the maintenance of health and in the prevention, diagnosis, improvement, or treatment of physical and mental illness."^{vii} Definitions of ethnomedicine vary slightly across disciplines, each focusing on different aspects of its integration with human society, biology, and the environment.

Within the discipline of anthropology, those who study human biology and have become interested in understanding how different cultures around the world deal with health, sickness, and medical systems are called 'Medical Anthropologists.' Medical Anthropologists look at what causes diseases and illnesses, how people try to prevent and manage them, and the practices and strategies different communities have developed to cope with health problems. This field combines insights from both biology and culture to study human health. They view ethnomedicine as integral to a human society's worldview and daily practices. Their term encompasses the medical treatments a community uses and the underlying cultural beliefs about health, disease, and healing.^{viii}

Anthropologist George Foster, a pioneer in the field of medical anthropology, described ethnomedicine as "those beliefs and practices relating to disease which are the products of indigenous cultural development and are not explicitly derived from the conceptual framework of modern medicine." This definition highlights ethnomedical systems' cultural and indigenous roots, distinguishing them from the institutionalized, modern biomedical framework. Foster emphasizes that ethnomedicine is tied to Indigenous groups' cultural practices and belief systems, reflecting a unique understanding of health, illness, and healing that differs from Western medical paradigms.^{ix} Claude Lévi-Strauss, another influential figure, focused on the symbolic nature of healing in indigenous practices. He argued that in many traditional societies, healing rituals operate on a physiological and symbolic level, influencing how the patient perceives their illness.^x

Sociologists examine ethnomedicine from the perspective of its social role, considering how customary medical procedures are ingrained in a community's social structure. For sociologists, ethnomedicine is seen as a cultural response to illness, a system that aligns with a group's social hierarchy, kinship structures, and religious practices. For instance, Durkheim believed that traditional societies and communities, often governed by religious and collective practices, create systems of meaning through rituals, which include healing practices. Traditional medicine, in this regard, might not only be about curing diseases but also about reinforcing social cohesion and collective beliefs. It could serve a social function, where health and healing are entangled with a society's religious and social

structures. Traditional medical systems, like religious ceremonies and practices, help communities maintain order, reinforce moral values, and explain otherwise unfathomable life events, like illness or death.^{xi}

Botanists and zoologists have a more empirical approach to ethnomedicine, by determining and focusing on the pharmacological properties of plants and animals used in traditional healing practices. Ethnobotanist Richard Evans Schultes, the father of modern ethnobotany, defined ethnomedicine as "the use of plants by indigenous people for medicinal purposes." He emphasized that traditional cultures frequently possess a profound awareness of the flora and fauna in their surroundings, highlighting the intimate connection between indigenous ecological knowledge and medical practices.^{xii}

On the other hand, zoologists have made contributions to ethnomedicine through their research and study of the relationships that exist between plants and animals, by observing how animals self-medicate by consuming specific plants when ill. This field, known as zoo pharmacognosy, demonstrates the intricate connections between human and animal medicinal practices and the broader ecosystem.^{xiii}

Environmental historians approach ethnomedicine by examining the historical and ecological context in which these practices developed. They focus on how indigenous knowledge systems have been shaped by the environment they inhabit and how these practices have evolved. Carolyn Merchant, an environmental historian, highlighted how native practices in the Americas, Africa, and Asia were closely tied to local ecosystems and played a significant role in the sustainable management of natural resources.^{xiv} In this perspective, ethnomedicine addresses both health issues and the ecological harmony that exists between humans and the natural world.

Historians who are working on tribes and indigenous research scholars emphasize the role of ethnomedicine in preserving cultural identity and indigenous knowledge systems. Their identity is often rooted in their cultural practices and belief systems developed through intergenerational transmission of knowledge. They highlight that traditional healing practices are deeply connected with spiritual beliefs, oral traditions, and the historical lived experiences of indigenous peoples. For instance, Native American ethnomedicinal or healing practices are often passed down through generations as part of a broader worldview that sees health as a balance between physical, emotional, and spiritual well-being.^{xv}

Ethnomedicine thus, bridges the gap between culture, ecology, and health. It is studied not only for its efficacy in treating diseases but also for its role in maintaining biodiversity, preserving cultural heritage, and promoting sustainable use of natural resources. The diverse definitions across anthropology,

sociology, botany, and other fields reflect the differences and connections of ethnomedicine as both a scientific and cultural phenomenon. We shall discuss evolution of ethnomedicine during different historical states:

A Pre-historic Society's Perspective

The study of traditional medical practices in diverse cultural contexts, or ethnomedicine, provides an insight into how societies have historically interacted with their natural environment to promote healing and well-being. This field draws from anthropological and botanical studies, tracing back to the earliest human societies that emphasized the use of plants, for rituals, and symbolic interpretations for health and diseases. It captures the diversity of human interactions with the natural world, which goes beyond simple biological survival to include social, spiritual, and cultural dimensions.

Archaeological evidence provides valuable insights into the use of plants by the Palaeolithic, Neolithic, and early agrarian societies. The knowledge and use of plants by early Palaeolithic societies, particularly Neanderthals, demonstrate a remarkable understanding of their natural surroundings and their medicinal resources. Fossil records and archaeological excavations reveal that as early as 60,000 years ago, Neanderthals were utilizing plants for their therapeutic properties. This evidence of the practice comes from the excavation findings at the grave of a Neanderthal man at Shanidar Cave in present-day Iraq, where pollen analysis of the burial site uncovered numerous plants with known medicinal value. This discovery suggests that these early humans recognized the healing potential of specific flora and engaged in the ceremonial or symbolic use of plants in burial practices.^{xvi}

The transition from the Palaeolithic to the Neolithic period, marked by the beginning of agriculture, saw significant advancements in human knowledge and interaction with the natural world they inhabited, particularly in using plants and natural resources for medicinal purposes. Excavations and archaeological evidence from Neolithic sites suggest relevant findings that the early agrarian societies continued and expanded upon the ethnobotanical knowledge. This knowledge was integral to their survival, as they relied on plants for food and treating ailments and injuries from hunting. One of the most remarkable evidence of plant usage in Neolithic societies comes from examining Ötzi the Iceman, a well-preserved mummy discovered in the Alps and dated to around 3300 BCE. Among Ötzi's possessions were fragments of medicinal plants, including the birch fungus (*Fomitopsis betulina*), which is well known for its antibacterial and anti-inflammatory characteristics, and a charcoal pouch that may have been used for digestive health or antiseptic purposes. These findings could possibly affirm that Ötzi's medicinal items, like the birch fungus and charcoal, were integral to Neolithic communities' daily life and

survival strategies.^{xvii} This reveals a comprehensive knowledge of plant-based treatments and remedies in Neolithic Europe. Furthermore, excavations conducted from Çatalhöyük, one of the most prominent Neolithic settlements in present-day Turkey, have also revealed shreds of evidence of the use of wild plants, through the application of strontium isotope analysis, such as poppy and juniper, with possible medicinal applications, utilized in a context of integrated crop and sheep management.^{xviii} This deliberate cultivation and selective use of plants points to an emerging body of knowledge emphasizing flora's medicinal value, ritual significance, and the nutritional value of the plants identified in archaeological findings.

A further indication that early farmers were actively choosing plants for both culinary and medicinal purposes came from the discovery of charred plant remnants and seeds in Neolithic sites in both Europe and Asia. The recovery of seeds from plants such as *Papaver somniferum* (opium poppy) from the early Neolithic site of Kouphvouno, southern Greece supports the argument that Neolithic people were aware of analgesic substances, which were used to alleviate pain or induce sedation.^{xix}

The interconnection between ethnobotanical practices and the emerging agricultural economy is further evidenced by the fact that certain plants, which were initially gathered from the wild for their medicinal qualities, were later cultivated. Archaeological excavations in Jericho, one of the oldest continuously inhabited cities, uncovered evidence of the deliberate cultivation of herbal plants, which were likely used in medical treatments.^{xx}

The archaeological evidence gathered and records from Neolithic Europe, the Near East, and other regions indicate that these early societies had developed a profound understanding of the medicinal properties of plants. This points to a growing body of ethnomedicinal knowledge and its integration into the daily lives of Neolithic societies. Ethnomedicine was a key part of their interaction with the environment, and its use is evidenced by their artifacts uncovered, plant remains in burial sites, and human remains, all of which speak to a cultured system of healing practices that would lay the foundation for later medical traditions.

A Global Historical Perspective

The utilization of plants for medicinal purposes has not merely persisted but has progressed significantly through the annals of history. As writing systems emerged and developed, societies began to document and organize their knowledge of medicinal plants, allowing for the preservation and dissemination of

ethnomedicinal practices across different cultures and communities. The advent of recorded traditions during this period in human history was a turning point in the evolution of ethnomedicine.

Ethnographic writings across different disciplines have systematically studied people and cultures. They have thrown critical insights into how societies understand, perceive, and practice medicine. Across the world, traditional medical practices reflect the intricate relationships between their culture, ecology, religion, and healing systems. This enabled a broader understanding of plant-based treatments, fostering cross-cultural interactions. As observed through anthropological studies, early humans revealed that they believed in plants that possess supernatural powers, attributing the cyclical nature of plant life to mystical forces.

Ethnomedicinal Practices in Ancient Egypt

The Egyptians were pioneers in documenting their medicinal knowledge. Their writings offer a well-documented deep connection between plants, medicine, and religion. Herodotus, the ancient historian, also described the Egyptians as meticulous in their study of plants, which they categorized according to their appearance and medicinal use.

The use of a wide array of plants in everyday life and ceremonies by the ancient Egyptians and physicians demonstrated a comprehensive grasp of nature. The blue and white lotus, which grew along the Nile River, was used in various religious ceremonies to symbolize fertility and rebirth.^{xxi} Similarly, myrrh, an aromatic resin, was revered and significant in Egyptian religious rites.^{xxii} Egyptians worshipped onions in addition to eating them, believing that their concentric rings symbolized the universe. It was frequently buried with the deceased. Ancient Greek athletes consumed large amounts of it in the belief that it would "balance" their blood and enhance their physical abilities.^{xxiii} The Egyptian influence extended beyond their borders, as they traded plant knowledge and resources, such as myrrh trees, with distant lands.^{xxiv}

Ethnomedicine in Greece and Rome

The Greeks and Romans also contributed significantly to the development of ethnomedicine, combining mythological beliefs with practical applications of plant knowledge. According to Greek mythology, the twelve Gods who made the summit of Mt. Olympus in Northern Greece as their home had a favorite plant, often associated with their divine powers. Zeus, the chief god, adopted the oak tree, symbolizing his strength. The goddess of wisdom, Athena, revered the olive tree, a highly valued tree that procured timber, fruit, and oil.^{xxv} The god of war, Aries chose the ash tree which supplied him with

shafts for spears.^{xxvi} The goddess of agriculture, Demeter, was propitiated by offering poppies to ensure a good harvest. The god of the underworld, Hades, was pleased by daffodils, which protected the earth against volcanic eruption and seismic activities.^{xxvii} These plants were sacred and widely used in medicinal and agricultural practices.

Roman contributions to ethnomedicine were influenced mainly by the work of Pliny the Elder, who had a lifelong interest in every aspect of the natural world, compiled extensive studies on the medicinal properties of plants. His work, *Natural History*, in 34 volumes described the use of various herbs and plants to treat animal bites, prevent diseases, and even concoct love potions. His collection of plant lore and study was of great work. For instance, since many mushrooms are poisonous, eating them could be dangerous. Even those that venomous snakes have breathed on become poisonous. After rubbing radishes on the skin, toxic animals refrained from biting. He was familiar with many plants that might fend against bites from snakes, spiders, scorpions, and crazy dogs. He also talked about plants with aphrodisiac qualities, or "love potions." His other findings included that grapevines detest radishes and should never be planted close to them, while cucumbers creep toward water and away from oil.^{xxviii} The practice of recording and classifying plant knowledge in Roman times profoundly impacted medieval European medicine.

Ethnomedicine in Indigenous Societies of the Americas

Native American tribes in the Americas created complex medical systems based on a profound knowledge of their natural surroundings. Early anthropologists and explorers recorded these customs, which frequently emphasized a holistic understanding of health, according to which the body, mind, and spirit are all interrelated. Shamans, also known as medicine men, are essential as go-betweens between these communities' material and spiritual realms.

The Cherokee people held that all living things, including plants, animals, and natural forces, possessed spirits, and that harmony between these beings was necessary for good health and well-being. To ascertain the medical applications of plants, healers communicated with the spirits of the plants, these healers followed conservation practices, gathering only a part of the plants they came across. Disease and imbalance were believed to arise when humans disturbed the natural order, as seen in the myth of "The Origin of Disease and Medicine," where animals punished humans with illness, while plants intervened to offer cures. Rituals like the "going to water" ceremony were vital for restoring balance within the individual and the community.^{xxix}

The Amazonian tribes of South America have created intricate systems of ethnomedicine, and their healers are referred to as shamans or curanderos.^{xxx} These people treat illnesses with a wide variety of local plants found in the Amazon rainforest. Ayahuasca is a South American hallucinogenic beverage that has been traditionally used for spiritual ceremonies, divinations, and the treatment of various psychosomatic ailments. It is a psychedelic infusion. It is thought that the shaman can access the spirit world, converse with the spirits, and determine the root causes of both spiritual and physical illnesses through the ritualistic use of ayahuasca.^{xxxii} These practices present a deeper spiritual connection of the indigenous healing practices in the Americas, where illness is often seen as stemming from both physical and metaphysical causes.

Traditional Medicine in Asia

Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), another major ethnomedical system, is grounded in balance and harmony, particularly the concept of *yin* and *yang* - opposing forces that must be balanced to maintain health. Traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) is thousands of years old. Its fundamental idea is that the body is filled with Qi, a vital life force. Illness and disease can arise from the imbalance of any Qi. The most widely accepted explanation for this illness in TCM is a disruption in the flow of *Qi*, and treatments aim to restore the balance of *yin* and *yang*.

The ancient Chinese believed people are connected to nature and subject to its influences, seeing themselves as microcosms of the greater cosmos. The idea of balance between illness and wellness is crucial, so TCM uses individualized care to bring this equilibrium back. Herbal medicine, cupping therapy, acupuncture, qigong/ tai chi exercises, and moxibustion therapy of burning herbal leaves near the body are among the most common therapies in TCM. Notably, herbs such as *ginseng* and *gingko biloba* have been used for centuries in Chinese medicine and are still popular today for their purported health benefits.^{xxxiii}

Ethnomedicine in India

India represents a country marked by a vast cultural and geographical diversity. The country's richness has earned her a rank among the world's most biodiverse countries. This richness has paved the way for India's traditional healing practices through centuries of interaction between various cultural, religious, and ecological systems. India's diverse medical and healing practices reflect the country's diversity, encompassing a wide range of practices like Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani systems to the local

folk medicine of various tribal communities. It highlights the country's rich cultural significance of plant-based remedies, rituals, and healing methods.

Ayurveda System

Ayurveda, often considered the oldest documented system of medicine, is rooted in the Vedic period, around 1500 BCE. It is based on the principle that health is maintained through a balance of bodily humors, or *doshas*: *vata* (air and space), *pitta* (fire and water), and *kapha* (earth and water).^{xxxiii} This holistic approach emphasizes the relationship between body, mind, and spirit, considering disease as a disruption of this harmony. Ayurvedic practitioners use a variety of treatments, including dietary regulations, herbal medicines, massages, and spiritual practices like yoga and meditation to restore balance in the body.

The use of plants in Ayurveda is extensive. Herbs such as *Ashwagandha* (*Withania somnifera*), *Turmeric* (*Curcuma longa*), and *Tulsi* (*Ocimum tenuiflorum*) are prescribed for their healing properties and have been used for thousands of years.^{xxxiv} Each plant is understood in terms of its qualities (*guna*), potency (*virya*), and post-digestive effect (*vipaka*), making it essential for addressing the unique constitution of each patient. For example, *Ashwagandha* is considered to have strengthening properties and is used to rejuvenate the body, while *Tulsi* is valued for its anti-inflammatory and adaptogenic effects.^{xxxv}

Siddha Medicine in Southern India

Siddha medicine, an ancient system that originated in Tamil Nadu, traces its roots to the Tamil *Siddhars*, mystics and philosophers believed to have achieved supernatural powers through meditation and austerity. Its primary goal is to achieve physical health and a holistic harmony of mental, social, and spiritual well-being, aimed at promoting longevity. Like Ayurveda, Siddha medicine focuses on balancing bodily elements but also integrates alchemical practices and a deep understanding of human anatomy. Siddha medicine relies heavily on natural resources, utilizing a wide range of substances, including herbs, minerals, metals, marine, and animal products.^{xxxvi} This makes it a distinct system within India's broader ethnomedical landscape.

In addition, Siddha medicine also strongly emphasises personal hygiene, lifestyle, and the moral and spiritual conduct of the individual, believing that the mind and body are deeply interconnected.^{xxxvii} Herbs such as *Aloe vera* and *Neem* (*Azadirachta indica*) are frequently used in Siddha medicine to treat skin diseases, fevers, and digestive disorders. The inclusion of mineral-based drugs, such as those made

from sulfur, is a unique feature of Siddha medicine that differentiates it from other Indian healing systems.^{xxxviii}

Unani Medicine

Unani medicine, also known as Greco-Arab medicine, was introduced to India by Persian scholars and practitioners during the medieval period, particularly after the establishment of the Mughal Empire. The Unani system is based on the teachings of the Greek physician Hippocrates, the Father of medicine, and was further developed by Arab scholars like Avicenna (Ibn Sina).^{xxxix} It emphasizes the balance of four bodily humors: blood (*dam*), phlegm (*balgham*), yellow bile (*safra*), and black bile (*sauda*).^{xl}

Unani practitioners, called *hakims*, use a combination of dietary practices, herbal medicines, and therapeutic procedures such as cupping and massage to treat illness. Plants such as *Zafran* (saffron), *Zanjabeel* (ginger), and *Asal-us-Soos* (licorice) are commonly used for their anti-inflammatory, digestive, and tonic properties.^{xli} During the Mughal period, Unani medicine gained popularity in India and is still frequently used today, especially in northern areas. The way Persian medical philosophy has been incorporated into Indian society and demonstrates the vibrant intellectual exchange that has moulded India's ethnomedical customs.

Tribal and Folk Medicine

Apart from the well-known systems such as Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani, indigenous communities all over India have a rich heritage of ushering tribal and traditional medicine. These regionally customized local medicine systems frequently draw from the area's distinctive features, such as its available flora and customs that have been traditionally passed down through the years.

The Santhal tribe, of Sahibganj district's Rajmahal Hills, represents a rich ethnomedicine tradition entwined with their native wisdom and close interaction with the natural world. Their medicinal methods employ different plant species from different botanical groups to treat various illnesses, from burns and cholera to rheumatism and cancer. This elaborate medical system is based on the painstaking manufacture of medicines, which include combining, grinding, and boiling fruits, leaves, roots, and barks to make pastes, poultices, or medicinal liquids. For example, rheumatism is treated with steam made from a specially prepared herbal infusion, and tumors are treated with strong plasters made from plants.^{xlii} The Santhal ethnomedical tradition preserves their environment and cultural identity against the intrusions of modernity, demonstrating not only a deep knowledge of the native flora but also a sustainable attitude.

This continuous history highlights the tribe's tenacity and the priceless worth of their traditional knowledge.

The *Santhal* tribe of Jharkhand and West Bengal use *Chirata* (*Swertia chirata*) and *Bael* (*Aegle marmelos*) to treat ailments like malaria, dysentery, and digestive disorders. In the Western Ghats, the *Kurumba* tribe relies on herbal remedies for conditions ranging from fever to snakebites, with plants like *Nilavembu* (*Andrographis paniculata*) being essential for their ethnomedicine.^{xliii} These tribal communities view illness as not just a physical condition but one that is deeply connected with spiritual and environmental factors. Rituals and prayers often accompany the administration of herbal medicines, highlighting the spiritual dimensions of healing in these communities.^{xliv}

Tribal and Folk Medicine in the North-East Region

India's northeastern states are home to some of the world's largest collections of aromatic and medicinal plants. It is marked for its rich biodiversity. The varied physiography of the northeastern part of India includes plains, plateaus, mountains, and valleys. This region can be classified geographically into three types: the Meghalaya plateau, the northeastern hills and basin, and the Brahmaputra valley.^{xlv} Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, and Tripura are the states that make up North East India and are also often called the seven-sister states. In addition to its exceptional natural diversity, this region of India is a prime example of the nation's "unity in diversity." These states also house numerous ethnic and tribal groups, both native and immigrant, with vibrant physical and cultural traits.

These Indigenous tribes have developed their unique traditional knowledge and transmitted it within their communities from generation to generation. This wisdom stems from their long-term observation, needs, trial and error, personal experiences, and intuition. Their cultural identities heavily rely on this knowledge. Many ethnic communities continue to exist in isolated highlands and forests. They depend heavily on traditional knowledge, which has always been essential to their daily lives, providing them with food security, housing, rituals, and a healthcare system.

The state of Arunachal has been considered a storehouse for herbal medicine. Tribal groups like the Adi, Apatani, and Nyishi are known for using various medicinal herbs. Tribal medicine in the state is based on more than 5000 varieties of blooming plants that make up its incredible biodiversity. Orchids, as are other endemic species, are highly valued in Arunachal for their aesthetic beauty and medicinal qualities. Many conditions, including fever, discomfort, and digestive issues, are treated with medicinal

herbs. For example, the Apatani tribe uses *Centella asiatica* to heal wounds and enhance overall health, while the Adi community uses *Zanthoxylum armatum* to cure fever and rheumatism.^{xlvi}

The Bodo, Mishing, and Deori were some indigenous communities in Assam with a long history of using their own locally available resources for healing practices. The therapeutic qualities of medicinal plants like *Ocimum sanctum* (holy basil) and *Bambusa balcooa* (bamboo) are commonly used. Bamboo is famous in Assam and is utilized not only for building but also as traditional medicine, where the shoots are used to heal stomach problems. The tribal culture of Assam is rich in plant knowledge, which is transmitted orally.

In Meghalaya, the Khasi and Garo tribes dominate the ethnomedicinal landscape. The Khasi healers, a diverse group of people who treat a wide range of illnesses, are known for their proficiency in treating physical ailments, which does not seem to correlate to biomedical systems or musculoskeletal disorders.^{xlvii} They also use medicinal plants, including *Ageratum conyzoides* for anti-inflammatory purposes and *Eupatorium triplinerve* for treating fever and wounds. Meghalaya's hilly terrain and high rainfall contribute to its abundant plant diversity, allowing the Garo tribe to utilize plants like *Clerodendrum viscosum* to treat malaria and other infectious diseases.^{xlviii}

Manipur, a state rich in flora, is home to the Meitei and Naga communities, who have long been traditional medicine practitioners. *Zingiber officinale* (*Zingiberaceae*), *Cocos nucifera* (*Arecaceae*), *Oroxylum indicum* (*Bignoniaceae*), *Curcuma longa* (*Zingiberaceae*) and *Allium sativum* (*Liliaceae*) used by maximum number of Manipuri healers in maximum number of formulations.^{xlix} Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) is used extensively in the Meitei community, particularly for respiratory conditions including coughs and asthma. Tribal healers in the state are also well-known for using a variety of herbs, including *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemongrass) and aloe vera, to treat skin ailments.

Most of Mizoram's ethnomedical traditions are practiced by the Mizo people, who are primarily dependent on forest resources. The Mizo employs plants like *Dillenia indica* and *Hedyotis scandens* to cure common illnesses like fevers, coughs, and stomach problems. Additionally, the Mizo make herbal remedies from *Phyllanthus emblica* and *Terminalia chebula*, which are both used for their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities. Ethnomedicine in Mizoram is still closely linked to spiritual traditions, and native healers frequently conduct rituals in addition to using medicinal herbs.¹

The Tripuri and Reang tribes in Tripura uphold a long-standing custom of ethnomedicine, mainly employing plants like *Centella asiatica* and *Clerodendrum indicum*. The Reang tribe uses *Centella*

asiatica to promote wound healing and enhance cognitive function, and *Clerodendrum indicum* to treat respiratory ailments. Most medicines were made as extracts and used orally, with leaves being the most commonly used plant portion.^{li} Tripura's lush tropical woods are vital to the health of the indigenous people, especially in isolated and rural areas.

CONCLUSION

Ethnomedicine represents a profound intersection of culture, ecology, and health that spans thousands of years and encompasses a rich diversity of traditional knowledge systems worldwide. Rooted deeply in the close relationship between humans and their natural environment, ethnomedicine captures not just the physical aspects of healing but also the social, spiritual, and symbolic dimensions that define different cultures' approaches to health and illness. This multidisciplinary field, studied through the lenses of anthropology, sociology, botany, zoology, and history, highlights the intricate ways in which indigenous communities have used plants, animals, rituals, and belief systems to maintain wellbeing. Despite the advan

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